

Complications after Mastectomy through Axillary Dissection in Females Presenting with Carcinoma of Breast

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Dr. Abdur Rehman Alvi**-Consultant Surgeon (FCPS, FRCS, FACS) ⁽²⁾ **Dr. Mobeen Adnan**-Senior Registrar (FCPS G. Surgery) ⁽³⁾ **Dr. Farhan Tahir**-Post Graduate Resident G. Surgery (FCPS).

Abstract

Axillary lymph node dissection is commonly performed as part of the primary management of breast carcinoma. Its value inpatient management, however, has recently been questioned. Few studies exist that document long term complications. In spite of complications it causes, its use in prognostication and planning adjuvant treatment in carcinoma breast is unquestioned.

This descriptive design study has been performed at the Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Gujranwala and its' basic objective is to assess the complications after mastectomy through the axillary dissection in females presenting with carcinoma of the breast.

Total 80 females fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study from the Ward of Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Gujranwala. Informed consent was obtained and the demographic profile was noted. Then all females undergo mastectomy by using axillary dissection under general anesthesia. All surgeries were performed by a single surgical team under the supervision of a supervisor to control bias. After surgery, females were shifted toward and discharged from there. Then females were followed-up in OPD for one month. After one month, females were asked for complications i.e. numbness, pain, swelling, infection, and limited movement. If females reported about these symptoms, then complications were noted. Mean age of women in this study was 49.99 ± 12.15 years. In 38(47.5%) women stage-I was diagnosed and 42(52.5%) women were diagnosed with stage-II. There were 38(47.5%) women who had reported numbness, 40(50%) women had pain, 42(52.5%) had swelling, 31(38.8%) women had limited movement of the shoulder and 52(65%) women suffered from infection.

Results of this study showed that there are certain complications after mastectomy through the axillary dissection in females. So concern regarding serious sequelae from axillary lymph node dissection should not be a major factor in treatment decisions.

Key Words: *Complications, Mastectomy, Axillary dissection, Carcinoma, Breast*

Background

Early breast cancer [EBC] constitutes 30% of breast cancer cases seen at regional cancer centres in the globe. Accordingly, breast cancer is the malignancy of the breast tissue which is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in the women worldwide. Globally it is accounted for 23% of all cancer cases. Almost 1.4 million women were diagnosed with breast cancer worldwide in 2008 and approximately 459,000 deaths were recorded. Incidence rates were much higher in more developed countries compared to less developed countries (71.7/100,000 and 29.3/100,000 respectively, adjusted to the World 2000 Standard Population) whereas the corresponding mortality rates were 17.1/100,000 and 11.8/100,000.

In Pakistan, the most frequently diagnosed cancer among females is also breast cancer, accounting for nearly one in nine female patients. Its incidence in Pakistan is 2.5 times higher than that in neighbouring countries like Iran and India. Traditionally the surgical management of breast cancer comprised wide local resection of the primary tumour and axillary lymph node dissection (ALND). Axillary status is the most important prognostic factor in breast cancer providing staging information and therefore largely defining treatment strategy.

Axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) has been part of breast cancer surgery since the description of the radical mastectomy. ALND reliably identifies nodal metastases and maintains regional control, but the contribution of local therapy to breast cancer survival is controversial.⁵ ALND, as a means for achieving local disease control, carries an indisputable and often unacceptable risk of complications such as seroma, infection, and lymphedema.

One study has found that after mastectomy through axillary dissection for breast carcinoma, the numbness, the pain was reported by 39% each, arm swelling by 25%, limitation of arm movement by 16%, infection by 11%. Another study reported that numbness was reported by 35% of patients, the pain was noted in 30%, arm swelling in 15%, and limitation of arm movement in 8%. While another study has reported that with axillary dissection, numbness was found in 28.5% cases, pain in 3% cases, and wound infection in 0% cases.

The rationale of this study is to assess the complications after mastectomy through the axillary dissection in females presenting with carcinoma of the breast. Axillary dissection is the most common procedure that is performed for mastectomy. It has also been reported that there are some complications develop after mastectomy through axillary dissection method. But no local evidence has been found which can help us to tackle with these complications as there incidence is the unknown in the local population. So we want to conduct this study to find the frequency of these complications can be assessed. This will help us to gain local magnitude and improve our practice.

2.0 Methods

This is a descriptive case study performed in the Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Gujranwala for six months using Non Probability, Consecutive sampling technique.

2.1 Sample Size

While using non probability consecutive sampling the sample size of the study is based on 80 cases is calculated with 95% confidence level, 6% margin of error and taking an expected percentage of limited movement i.e. 8% after mastectomy through the axillary dissection in females presenting with carcinoma of the breast

2.2 Inclusion Criteria

Females of age 30-70 years presenting with a medical record of breast carcinoma (Stage I & II) planned to undergo mastectomy through axillary dissection ASA I & II

2.3 Exclusion Criteria:

Patients with bilateral disease

Patients with recurrent breast lumps (carcinoma) or metastasized carcinoma

Females with deranged LFTs (ALT>40IU, AFSTF>40IU) and RFTs (serum creatinine>1.2mg/dl), hypertension (BP \geq 140/90mmhg), diabetics (BSR>186mg/dl)

Total 80 females fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study from the Ward of Department of Surgery, DHQ Hospital, Gujranwala. Informed consent was obtained and demographic profile (name, age, duration of breast cancer and contact) was noted. Then all females undergo mastectomy by using axillary dissection under general anesthesia. All surgeries were performed by a single surgical team under the supervision of a supervisor to control bias. After surgery, females were shifted toward and discharged from there. Then females were followed-up in OPD for one month. After one month, females were asked for complications i.e. numbness, pain, swelling, infection, and limited movement. If females reported about these symptoms, then complications were noted (as per operational definition).

2.4 Statistical Analysis

Data will be entered and analysed through in SPSS version 20. Quantitative variables like age will be presented as mean and standard deviation. Qualitative variables like gender, symptoms of acute abdomen and abdominal tuberculosis will be presented as frequency and percentage. Data will be stratified for age (40-60, 61-80years), gender (male/female) and different symptoms of the acute abdomen at the time of presentation. Post-stratification, Chi-Square test will be applied to compare abdominal tuberculosis in stratified groups. P-value ≤ 0.05 will be taken as significant.

3.0 Results

Mean age of women in this study was 49.99 ± 12.15 years. Minimum and maximum age of women was 30 and 70 years. (*Table-1*)

Table-1 - Descriptive statistics for the age of women

<i>n</i>	80
<i>Mean</i>	49.99
<i>SD</i>	12.15
<i>Minimum</i>	30
<i>Maximum</i>	70

ASA status of women showed that 40(50%) women had ASA-I and 40(50%) had AS-II. (*Table-2*)

Table-2 - ASA Status of patients

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>ASA-I</i>	40	50%
<i>ASA-II</i>	40	50%
<i>Total</i>	80	100%

Mean duration of diagnosis of breast lump was 3.10 ± 1.31 years. Minimum and maximum duration of diagnosis were 1 and 5 years respectively. (*Table-3*)

Table-3 - Descriptive statistics for the duration of diagnosis of breast lump

<i>n</i>	80
<i>Mean</i>	3.10
<i>SD</i>	1.31
<i>Minimum</i>	1
<i>Maximum</i>	5

In 38(47.5%) women stage-I was diagnosed and 42(52.5%) women were diagnosed with stage-II (*Table-4*)

Table-4 - Stage of Carcinoma

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Stage-I</i>	38	47.5%
<i>Stage-II</i>	42	52.5%
<i>Total</i>	80	100

There were 38(47.5%) women who had reported numbness, 40(50%) women had pain, 42(52.5%) had swelling, 31(38.8%) women had limited movement of the shoulder and 52(65%) women suffered from an infection after mastectomy through axillary dissection. (*Table-5*)

Table-5 - Complications observed during follow up

	Complications		Total
	Yes	No	
Numbness	38(47.5%)	42(52.5%)	80
Pain	40(50%)	40(50%)	80
Swelling	42(52.5%)	38(47.5%)	80
Limited Movement	31(38.8%)	49(61.3%)	80
Infection	52(65%)	28(35%)	80

In all age group frequency of numbness, pain, swelling and infection were statistically same. However limited movement significantly differs in age groups. The numbness was the highest in the age group >60 years (57.9%) followed by 44.8% in 30-45 years women and 43.8% women who were 46-60 years of age. The frequency for pain was highest in the age group 46-60 years (56.3%) followed by 30-45 years age group (51.7%) and 36.8% in women who were >60 years. Swelling and limited movement frequency were highest in the age group 46-60 years. However, the infection was the same in the age group 30-45 and 46-60 years i.e. 65.6% and in the group >60 years it was 63.2% respectively. (*Table-6*)

Table-6 - Complications observed during follow up in terms of age of women

	30-45 Years		46-60 Years		>60 Years		p-value
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Numbness	13(44.8%)	16(55.2%)	14(43.8%)	18(56.3%)	11(57.9%)	8(42.1%)	0.581
Pain	15(51.7%)	14(48.3%)	18(56.3%)	14(43.8%)	7(36.8%)	12(63.2%)	0.396
Swelling	15(51.7%)	14(48.3%)	17(53.1%)	15(46.9%)	10(52.6%)	9(47.4%)	0.994
Limited Movement	11(37.9%)	18(62.1%)	17(53.1%)	15(46.9%)	3(15.8%)	16(84.2%)	0.030
Infection	19(65.5%)	10(34.5%)	21(65.6%)	11(34.4%)	12(63.2%)	7(36.8%)	0.982

Women whose duration of diagnosis was in between 1-2 years among them numbness was seen in 50% women, pain in 50% women, swelling in 53.8% women, limited movement in 42.3% women and infection in 65.4% women. However, women whose duration of disease was 3-5 years among them numbness was reported by 46.3% women, pain in 50%, swelling in 48.1% women, limited movement in 63% women and infection in 35.2% women. However, none of these complications were significantly associated with the duration of diagnosis of diseases in women. (*Table-7*)

Table-7 - Complications observed during follow up in terms of duration of diagnosis

	1-2 Years		3-5 Years		p-value
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Numbness	13(50%)	13(50%)	25(46.3%)	29(53.7%)	0.765
Pain	13(50%)	13(50%)	27(50%)	27(50%)	1.000
Swelling	14(53.8%)	12(46.2%)	28(51.9%)	26(48.1%)	0.867
Limited Movement	11(42.3%)	15(57.7%)	20(37%)	34(63%)	0.650
Infection	17(65.4%)	9(34.6%)	35(64.8%)	19(35.2%)	0.960

The numbness was reported by 52.6%, pain in 47.4% women, swelling in 50% women, limited movement in 39.5% women and infection in 60.5% women who presented with stage-I. While women with stage-II among them these complications were seen as i.e. swelling in 42.9% women, pain in 52.4% women, swelling in 54.8% women, limited movement in 38.1% women and infection in 69% women. Frequency of complications was statistically the same in women with stage-I and with stage-II. (**Table-8**)

Table-8 - Complications observed during follow up in terms of stage of the disease

	Stage-I		Stage-II		p-value
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Numbness	20(52.6%)	18(47.4%)	18(42.9%)	24(57.1%)	0.382
Pain	18(47.4%)	20(52.6%)	22(52.4%)	20(47.6%)	0.654
Swelling	19(50%)	19(50%)	23(54.8%)	19(45.2%)	0.670
Limited Movement	15(39.5%)	23(60.5%)	16(38.1%)	26(61.9%)	0.899
Infection	23(60.5%)	15(39.5%)	29(69%)	13(31%)	0.425

4.0 Discussion

Pakistani women show an incidence rate of 50/100,000 and in the neighbouring country India, with similar socio-cultural background the incidence rate is 19/100,000. The pattern of rapid premenopausal increases in breast cancer is also seen in Pakistan, but breast cancer risk plateaus after the age of 45 years. Locally advanced breast cancer (LABC) which is also a common presentation includes non-metastatic tumours larger than 5 cm in diameter or that involve skin or chest wall. These also include tumours associated with fixed axillary lymph nodes and with ipsilateral supraclavicular, infraclavicular or internal mammary nodal involvement.

The disease burdens of cancer are rarely considered for developing countries like Pakistan. The South Karachi Cancer Registry suggests that the age-standardized annual rate of breast cancer in Pakistan is 69.1 per 100,000, a figure equivalent to European and North American rates. In fact, Pakistan's population boasts the highest rate of breast cancer amongst all Asian countries (excluding Jews in Israel) as over 90,000 women suffer from breast cancer annually.

Near the end of the 19th century, a variety of surgical techniques were described for the treatment of breast cancer. Moore recommended complete removal of the breast, Gross, excision of the axillary contents when nodes were involved, Volkmann, removal of pectoral fascia and excision of both pectoral muscles in certain cases; Kuster, asystematic clearing out of the axilla and Heidenhan, removal of superficial portion of the pectoralis major muscle and the entire muscle when the cancer is adherent to the chest wall. In 1891 Halstedian mastectomy became the hallmark of "Proper" surgery.

ALND as part of the surgical therapy for breast cancer has come under increased scrutiny over the last several years, mainly due to the introduction of the Sentinel Lymph Node (SLN) biopsy technique to assess the status of the axillary nodes. This technique has the advantage of avoiding ALND in those patients with pathologically negative nodes and of identifying those nodes at the highest risk of disease. This allows the pathologist to focus their efforts more thoroughly on those nodes most likely to be positive.

The principal downside of the SLN biopsy technique is the possibility of a false-negative result, i.e., the sentinel node is negative, but there is disease elsewhere within the axilla that is not identified. Consequently, the disease is left behind and the patient's disease status is downstaged with resultant under treatment.

The long term morbidity of ALND in inexperienced hands is minimal, as there are multiple factors in addition to the extent of axillary dissection contributing to the morbidity. ALND should remain a reasonable treatment option (especially in Pakistan) until long term recurrence and survival data are available with the SLN technique, particularly for patients with invasive cancers more than 2 Cm in size. In this study 38(47.5%) women presented with stage-I and 42(52.5%) presented with stage-II. In these study women with stage -I and stage-II were included.

In a study at AIIMS, 16% of patients had stage I and 74% had stage II disease, whereas in developed countries 50–60% patients present with stage I disease. Preetinder Brar in his study reported that on pathological staging 14% of patients were in stage I, 69% were in stage II and 17% were in stage III. Most of the patients presenting to doctors in Pakistan have stage III (34.8%) or stage II (32.2%) disease at the time of diagnosis. In a study, only 3.3% of patients had stage II disease. In another study, 2 (3.9%) patients had TNM stage II, 42 (82.4%) had TNM stage III and 8 (15.9%) had TNM stage IV disease.

In this study there were 38(47.5%) women who reported for numbness, 40(50%) women had pain, 42(52.5%) had swelling, 31(38.8%) women had limited movement of the shoulder and 52(65%) women suffered from an infection after mastectomy through axillary dissection.

Brar studied the incidence and severity of complications of ALND. In his findings he showed that numbness, pain were reported by 39% each, arm swelling by 25%, limitation of arm movement by 16%, infection by 11%.⁶ Frequency of complications after mastectomy through axillary dissection was higher in this study as that of reported by Brar study. This difference might be due to the difference in sample size or might be due to some other methodological parameters patients' selection or other differences in management after mastectomy through axillary dissection.

Ivens et al. assessed morbidity by administering a questionnaire to 126 consecutive patients who had undergone full ALND at least 6 months previously. Of these patients, 54 had undergone surgery at least 2 years previously. Problems reported by the group included numbness [70%], pain [33%], weakness [25%], swelling [24%] and stiffness [15%]. In no case were the symptoms described as severe, though the symptoms interfered with daily living in 39% of cases. Patients who had undergone surgery more than 2 years previously reported a lower incidence of pain and numbness though the difference was not statistically significant. Post complications of ALND in this study were much higher as that of reported by Ivens. However, Ivens reported much higher frequency for numbness as compared to this study i.e. 47.5% (This study) vs. 70% by (Ivens).

A cross sectional study was conducted by Marc. A. Warmuth, et al. on 432 stage 1 and 2 breast cancer patients. Patients had undergone surgery 2–5 years previously. The numbness was reported by 35% of patients, pain by 30%, arm swelling by 15% and limitation of arm motion by 8%. 8% reported episodes of infection or inflammation at some point since the diagnosis of breast carcinoma. Another study has reported that with axillary dissection, numbness was found in 28.5% cases, pain in 3% cases, and wound infection in 0% cases.

Early arm oedema is said to occur in about half of the patients after axillary dissection. The majority, develop some degree of oedema, often so slight that they were unaware of it. The higher body mass index before and after operation increases the risk of lymphoedema.

Published studies reporting subjective data on upper extremity function after breast cancer operations often contradict each other, making interpretation difficult. Many variables, including age, treatment of the dominant side, and socioeconomic status have all been shown to influence the reporting of arm complications. Arm and shoulder pain after SLND alone have been reported subjectively by as many as 36% of patients.⁹⁹ The subjective self-reporting of post-ALND lymphedema by questionnaire has varied even more, with incidence rates of up to 49%. The use of ALND is questioned in recent years; controversy arises because of inherent morbidity following ALND without directly contributing to survival.

Complications after surgery for breast carcinoma include lymphedema of the arm, numbness of arm and chest wall, restriction of movement of arm, pain, and infection in arm and chest wall. Because of this morbidity following routine ALND, various alternatives have been advocated like axillary sampling¹⁰³, limited level I dissection and sentinel lymph node biopsy. Keeping in mind the results of this study it can be said that mild symptoms of ALND are very common and severe complications very rare. Concerns regarding serious sequelae from ALND should not be a major factor in the treatment decision.

Conclusion

Results of this study showed that there are certain complications after mastectomy through the axillary dissection in females. So concern regarding serious sequelae from axillary lymph node dissection should not be a major factor in treatment decisions. Prevalence of these milder symptoms, however, should be considered when physicians counsel patients and make recommendations about the decision to proceed with an axillary lymph node dissection.

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